

Emerging Trends and Challenges in Post COVID - 19 World of Education System

Patil, J.B.

Assistant Prof., KCES's College of Education & Physical Education Jalgaon

Abstract

Education is important for a country like India for its development and economic growth along with social development. It typically comprises under graduate, post graduate degrees as well as pre - doctoral and doctoral programmes. It also plays a key role in producing teachers for the field of education. Therefore, it is essential for survival hence; this paper gives an insight into the recent trends in the post covid -19 world of Education system. In Spite of the significant growth of higher education in the past few years, it is still in a danger zone due to several challenges like the quota system, privatization, etc. Hence, various methods need to be found to improve the COVID-19 has expedited digital adoption in the education industry and encouraged educators to rethink how best to deliver education to students. The field of online teaching & learning has given everyone a chance to experience new learning, develop new perspectives, and accept new trend of education while heading into the great unknown field of imparting knowledge with technology. The teachers, students and parents are facing challenges, as the practice and assessment of online education is limited in the variety and modes in which they are allocated is affecting the students and teachers ending that they are experiencing a number of challenges. Adapting to online environment can be a challenge for both facilitators and students. The technical issues, complexity, sequencing of activities is among the major obstacles to the incorporation of multimedia application in the learning. This paper gives Ten identified major challenges

Key Words: - *Emerging Trends, Challenges, Post COVID-19 World, Education Syst*

Introduction

. According to some educationalists, including Anthony Seldom, vice chancellor for the University of Buckingham, and Glyn Davis, former vice chancellor for the University of Melbourne, the sector will fragment into more specialized institutions—all adding value with much more intensive use of digital technology. They also expect the growth of online programs in an attempt to develop new revenue models and find the next wave of innovation.

The pandemic is not the only driver for change. Governments' appetite for funding education that is misaligned with national and employer priorities or less-than-immediately applicable research is declining. Students continue to demand more flexibility and personalization. And in concert with the globalization of education and research, digital technology promises to bring about better, faster, and more relevant outcomes from almost anywhere.

The growing popularity of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) and open-source learning platforms is in part a response to these pressures at much lower cost. Together with more specialized employer demands, such disruptive innovation has the potential to give rise to a new

breed of degree-level qualifications made up of stacked credentials from different sources. For primary and secondary schools, the situation varies in each country depending on the country's COVID-19 policies. Some schools have announced that younger learners can return at reduced capacity whereas others continue to offer distance learning. The challenge for universities and schools alike is not merely a question of balancing in-person and online education personalized or otherwise in response to a health and safety challenge.

Objectives of the Study

1) To know about the Emerging Trends in Post COVID -19 World of Education System.

2) To know about the Challenges in Post COVID -19 World of Education System

Methodology

This research is a descriptive study. The necessary secondary data was collected from various websites including those of Government of India, magazines, journals, other publications, etc. This data was then analyzed and reviewed to arrive at the inferences and conclusions.

I) Emerging Trends in Post COVID -19 World of Education System

Seven trends have emerged in conversations with customers and leaders across secondary and higher education systems.

1) Flexible Learning: - Most universities are implementing social distancing measures on campus and in student accommodations when they reopen. A vast majority of universities across the world are offering a blend of face-to-face and online teaching and assessment for at least the 2020-21 academic years. Many schools are following shorter-term sprint plans rather than year-long strategies. Few have set out longer term plans, and none seem to be envisioning a return to the way things have been for years. Educators now agree that personalized education yields better learning outcomes, and technology has accelerated this process. The so-called flip classroom model, where students absorb new materials as homework and use classroom time for discussion, attempts to personalize the process of learning, with some success. But the content and the pace of progress remains fixed. For teaching to be more effective, educators agree that they should focus on how students are engaging with the material and use technology to drive engagement and interaction.

2) Employability: - The pandemic prompted a newfound urgency to reinvent curricula and offer flexible learning. There is more interest in stackable learning, defined as taking a selection of academic programs that can stack together to achieve a certificate or degree. For years, community colleges and further education institutions have been adopting alternative certifications in an effort to keep up with the pace of change in the jobs demanded by the labor market. While bachelor's degrees are still sought after, educators are introducing shorter courses and stackable credentials that better meet the needs of their learners. They are offering flexibility on cost, time commitment, and the ability to gain certification in emerging specializations in fast-changing fields like technology and healthcare. Stackable learning is a good fit for students balancing their education with full or part-time jobs, not least because it recognizes the knowledge and skills gained through activities beyond traditional degree courses like certificates, digital badges, and apprenticeships.

3) Assessment: - With most teaching moving online, educators need ways to assess learning remotely. In response to the pandemic, many countries either cancelled or postponed their national end-of-year tests for secondary schools.

Other schools and universities attempted to move their exams online to wrap up the full academic year for their students. According to Chris Fryer, senior systems administrator for digital education, they moved to the cloud and scaled their capacity to over 2,000 students. The scalability and security of their online infrastructure was critical to facilitating this move.

Over the medium and long term, educators have an opportunity to rethink assessment as a whole and experiment with technologies that enhance various aspects of assessment. Testing should be more authentic and continuous, assessing skills in a more realistic way. Technologies like machine learning can ease teachers' workloads by offering automated feedback on assignments. For example, revisely is an education company that helps teachers give better feedback on students' writing assignments and performs plagiarism checks on essays.

4) Research: - Research will continue to internationalize and become more collaborative. The future of research is less certain than its predicament. For hundreds of years, research has informed teaching, and a university's reputation is still in large part based on its research. At least two major shifts promise to

rebalance basic versus applied research, as well collaboration not only between universities but entire nations. Firstly, governments are increasingly insistent on more immediately applicable research, citing the impact of independent research institutes funded by government and industry. Secondly, universities, research institutes, or even entire nations tackling the same opportunities cannot individually address global challenges.

5) Student Wellbeing: - Online learning has the disadvantage of less social interaction and connection to the campus. Together with stress from the global pandemic, more remote courses may exacerbate mental health conditions among digital learners. Even before the pandemic, educators struggled to keep up with demand for mental health support. Research by Boston University shows that mental health problems correlate with dropping out of college. Some universities are using data analytics to gain insights on which students are struggling and intervene early to support them. In response to the crisis, some universities have set up hotlines and chat bots, which help reduce the administrative burden of increasing call volume and enable health professionals to spend more time with students. For example, the Los Angeles Unified School District in the US set up a cloud-

based call center to provide mental health support to students and families a few days after the outbreak. Therefore, universities are rethinking the layout and functionality of campuses and student accommodation, partly in response to the global health and safety challenge.

6) Privacy and Security: - Educational institutions will focus more on security and privacy of online systems. With much of learning taking place online, educational institutions and research centers are becoming even more vulnerable to cyber-attacks. Earlier this year, malware known as Net walker hit several universities in the US, successfully encrypting systems on university networks and requesting funds in return for access to their files. Some reports indicate one of the schools were targeted because of its proprietary research related to COVID-19 vaccines. In response to these attacks, and to protect against future threats, universities are using security features such as data encryption, multifactor authentication, and virtual private networks (VPN).

Technology can help mitigate such incidents and guard against theft of intellectual property. Educators are also becoming more vigilant when

it comes to student data and privacy. Attackers are increasingly threatening to reveal student and faculty personally identifiable information. With more and more students conducting their educational activities online—videoconferencing, taking online exams, and more—academic institutions increasingly have to scrutinize vendor contracts to ensure compliance with laws protecting student security and privacy. They also need to prioritize security awareness among faculty, staff, and students. Educational institutions have also been conducting more training for their staff and students around the security of online systems.

7) Digital Divide: - Digital learning is here to stay. Yet, many learners do not have access to the technology necessary for online learning, be it devices or a reliable internet connection. This problem is particularly acute for primary and secondary school students. There are promising solutions that are helping students connect no matter their location. US-based technology company Kajeet Inc, which runs on AWS, is providing learners with hotspot devices that are simple to use and are compliant with federal laws protecting student's access to online content. Already, a school district in Virginia, US, has started taking Kajeet's Education Broadband™ to those communities –they are

installing the technology on buses that deployed in areas with no connectivity. The wireless signal can reach homes within 100 meters of the parked bus or the size of a football field. This is one example of a cloud solution that can help bridge the educational gap, which will be increasingly important as more schools decide to extend online learning in the coming months. Other solutions include using low-bandwidth technology, including chat apps, to learn and connect with students and parents.

II) Challenges in Post COVID -19 World of Education System

. The teachers, students and parents are facing challenges, as the practice and assessment of online education is limited in the variety and modes in which they are allocated is affecting the students and teachers ending that they are experiencing a number of challenges. Adapting to online environment can be a challenge for both facilitators and students. The technical issues, complexity, sequencing of activities is among the major obstacles to the incorporation of multimedia application in the learning. Major identified challenges are as follows:

Challenge 1- Economic Disparity:

The economic impact on household is likely to widen the inequalities in education. Many times, due to financial constraint student fail to get the benefit of online teaching and learning because some students do not have the financial stability of buying smart phones, computer, laptop etc. needed to adapt to the new mode of instruction. Student's belonging from lower socioeconomic background lacks reading opportunities, parental support with their home work during school closure.

Challenge 2- Missing Technical Support

Around the world because of the high usage rate of online learning system people across the world are experiencing technical difficulties. In some country's challenge is faced because internet connection is unstable to cover the progressive e-learning needs, platforms are overloaded, resulting poor quality video and audio. Students in both urban and rural areas are struggling to bridge the 'homework gap'. The teachers and students are trying to encounter the issue of the bad internet connection during the online lessons, for which maximum time is wasted in connecting with the students and teachers.

Challenge 3- Lack of Technical Skills

Teachers, parents and students are not adapted to the use of technology equipment, skills and working conditions as they are familiar with the traditional method of teaching and learning. Teachers are not trained for conducting virtual classes along with this they have to bear extra expense to use numerous digital tools for conducting lectures and students are not friendly with the virtual mode of teaching.

Challenge 4- Stressful Living Conditions

Closure of academic institutions and movements restrictions obstructs routine of students and social support system. In some countries where children are provided with the childcare have put parents into terrible stress of finding new child care options. The impact of lost opportunities to learn and loss of freedom of movement as well as future uncertainties add layers of stress on everyone.

Challenge 5- Long hours of Work

The extended working hours for teachers and students are stressful and leave adverse psychological impact on them. Teachers try to connect with the parents, students, attend virtual schools, try to handle the amount of information and also plan the teaching strategy. They are overwhelmed by technical knowledge

they attain while they try to conduct the digital classes as well as frustrated when they face the issue for which they are neither prepared nor trained.

Challenge 6- Challenge for Weak Learners

Online learning is a kind of challenge for the students having language barrier, or those suffering from physical ailment, these students face a double problem multiplying the chances of falling behind.

Challenge 7- Data Security

Covid-19 outbreak, just as any other emergency has given a chance to digital criminals releasing the wave of cyber-attacks. Security of data is overlooked while meeting the objective of adapting to online learning, especially when temporary free subscription plans are offered by large e-learning software companies. Teachers and students from the initial days of lockdown have explored uncountable digital apps, tools to conduct their online lessons without paying due attention to the personal data that has been filled by the companies. It is important to keep the sensitive data safe from being stolen for digital tools that supports e-learning.

Challenge 8- Lack of Interaction

During COVID 19 students' motivation and learning progress is highly affected as during classroom teaching students are in eye-to-eye communication with each other, so that they can react to each other, sharing their experience, crack jokes, & develop understanding for nonverbal contact, and strengthening the social skills. For many students, a classroom has been a kind of sanctuary, which is now taken away. It is difficult to put into practice online teaching without in-person instructions. Online teaching and learning have put teachers and students in state of psychological stress resulting which most of them feel isolated, scared by the pandemic, lost their jobs, and fully disconnected.

Challenge 9- Missing Result Oriented Education

While online learning students miss to learn to deal with forms of discrimination, anxieties like stage fright, dealing with group mates of the opposite sex, and also imbibe emotions and attitude. Teachers are doubtful about the student's alertness during the class and it becomes difficult for them to assess the student's performance and the understanding of the concepts through online teaching to student as students are not accustomed of online examination and teachers of online evaluation,

which develop a huge gap in teaching learning process.

Challenge 10- Balance in work and study

While opting for online teaching and learning it is observed that students are not prepared to create balance in their work, family, and social lives along with their studies. There is the predictable stress for the completion of syllabus while ensuring safety and welfare. Students were also found to be poorly prepared for several e-learning competencies concerning the usage of Learning Management Systems

Indeed, academic institutions could not transform all of their academic curricula into an online resource overnight. Innovative solutions provided by institutions can only work as a support system to engage the teachers and students in the teaching learning process during this pandemic. The challenges faced while online teaching justifies the reasons and need to reinvent education along pathways too long that is blocked by negligence, arrogance and rigidity. The calamities check the preparedness for the future, so the challenges should be overcome with the passage of time.

Conclusion

Education is a fundamental right of every individual as it plays a prominent role in life. The spread of COVID19 has paused the life due to worldwide lockdown affecting the life of people, families and communities. Teaching models are changing and forcing universities, colleges, and schools to adjust their business and financial models. Declining enrollments, rising health and safety costs, a decline in international student enrollment, and cuts in public funding are posing new financial challenges for educational institutions across the world. Despite these challenges, educational institutions have an opportunity to innovate and thrive in this era of rapid change and uncertainty. New technologies are increasingly demonstrating how they can enhance student outcomes, make teaching more effective, and drive collaboration and engagement. To reap the full benefits of technology, educational institutions should embrace a culture of change, using this moment as an opportunity to experiment and innovate to meet the changing needs of their students.

References: -

1. Altbach, P. G., De Wit, H. (2020). Post-pandemic outlook for higher education

is bleakest for the poorest. *International Higher Education*, 102, 3 – 5.

2. Amemado, D. (2020). COVID-19: An unexpected and unusual driver to online education. *International Higher Education*, 102, 12 – 14.
3. Arnold, N., Brajkovic, L., Nikolaev, D., Zavalina, P. (2020). Tertiary Education and COVID-19: Impact and Mitigation Strategies in Europe and Central Asia. file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/ECATEandCOVID19longFINAL25May20.pdf.
4. Dhawan, S. (2020). Online learning: A panacea in the time of COVID-19 Crisis. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(1), 5–22.
5. Dill, E., Fischer, K., Mcmurtrie, B., Supiano, B. (2020). As corona virus spreads, moving classes online is the first step. What's next? *The Chronicle of Higher Education*. <https://www.chronicle.com/article/as-coronavirus-spreads-the-decision-to-moveclasses-online-is-the-first-step-what-comes-next/>
6. Flack, C. B., Walker, L., Bickerstaff, A., Earle, H., Margetts, C. (2020). Educator perspectives on the impact of COVID-19

- on teaching and learning in Australia and New Zealand. Pivot Professional Learning.
7. Jain Gunjan (2020). Emerging Trends & Education During & Post COVID 19: A Challenge. Solid State Technology, Volume 63 Issue -1s.
 8. Kara, Augustine (2020). COVID -19 Pandemic & Possible Trends for the future of Higher Education: - A Review, Journal of Education & Educational Development.
 9. Khadka, S., Hashmi, F. K., Usman, M. (2020). Preventing COVID-19 in low-and middle-income countries. Drugs & Therapy Perspectives, 36(6), 250-252.
 10. Marinoni, G. van't, Land, H. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 on global higher education. International Higher Education, 102, 7 –9.